

Corpus of OSCE Elections Monitoring Reports, 1995-2020

Michal Mochtak and Adam Drnovsky

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Contents

Overview	2
Citation Information	2
Variables	3
document_id	3
election_id	3
link	3
doc_type	3
head_of_mission	3
head_of_mission_state	3
core_experts	3
lto	3
experts	3
sto	3
sto_second_round	3
sto_third_round	3
election	4
election2	4
date1	4
date2	4
date3	4
cumulative_date	4
year	4
parliamentary	4
general	4
presidential	4
referendum	4
early_election	4
repeat_election	4
federal	4
local	5
municipal	5
provincial	5
mission_type	5
mission_type2	5
needs_assesment_m	5
election_assessment_m	5
expert_team_m	5
observation_m	5

limited_observ_m	5
support_team_m	5
referendum_m	5
country	5
region	5
region2	6
link_pdf	6
ecb_code	6
un_code	6
wb_code	6
wvs_code	6
eurostat_code	6
politIV_code	6
cw_code	6
vdem_code	6
nelda_code1	6
nelda_code2	6
mission_opening	6
ct_departure	6
lto_deployment	7
lto_departure	7
sto_deployment	7
sto_departure	7
sto_arrival_second_round	7
sto_departure_second_round	7
ct_nationality	7
lto_nationality	7
corpus_id	7
heading	7
heading_clean	7
level	7
tag	7
text	8
lem	8

Overview

This is a codebook for the corpus of election monitoring reports collected from the official repository of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) and its subsidiary Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights (ODIHR) ([link](#)). Monitoring reports stored as machine-readable pdf files were text-mined and re-organized into a convenient tabular format (i.e. data frame). The corpus covers the period of 1995-2020 and counts 415 reports parsed into 11 529 topical sections. As spreadsheet software (e.g. MS Excel, Libre Office Calc) is limited in how many characters can be stored in a cell, corpus data are made available in R’s native binary data format “RDS”. For information on how to read the archive, see instructions for R ([link](#)) and Python ([link](#)).

Citation Information

If you use the dataset, please cite: Mochtak, Michal, Adam Drnovsky, and Christophe Lesschaeve (2022): “Bias in the Eye of Beholder? 25 Years of Election Monitoring in Europe”. *Democratization*, 29 (5): 899-917. ([link](#)). To preserve the traceability of your analysis, do not forget to reference the actual version of the dataset as well (see the suggested format in the repository’s description field).

Variables

The dataset contains 69 variables. The following overview introduces all of them.

document_id

Unique document id per report.

election_id

Unique election id containing information on the type of report, country, and the election year.

link

Link to the election's website.

doc_type

Document type following the OSCE taxonomy: full report [FR], assessment mission report [AMR], technical mission report [TMR], observation [O], statement [S], recommendations [R], pre-election overview [PEO], expert visit [EV], expert group report [EGR], support team report [STR], preliminary statement [PS].

head_of_mission

Name of the head of mission.

head_of_mission_state

State of the head of mission (i.e. nationality).

core_experts

Number of core experts deployed.

lto

Number of long-term observers deployed.

experts

Number of experts deployed.

sto

Number of short-term observers deployed.

sto_second_round

Number of short-term observers deployed for the second round.

sto_third_round

Number of short-term observers deployed for the third round.

election

Type of election: presidential, parliamentary, general, local, referendum, and their combinations.

election2

Further specification of the election type (e.g. municipality, by-election, early election, etc.).

date1

First day of the first round of the election.

date2

First day of the second round of the election (if applicable).

date3

First day of the third round of the election (if applicable).

cumulative_date

If date2 (or date3) is reported, the cumulative date is a midpoint of the reported dates. If the election has just one round, cumulative_date is equal to date1.

year

Year of the election (extracted from cumulative_date).

parliamentary

Dummy variable for a parliamentary election.

general

Dummy variable for a general election.

presidential

Dummy variable for a presidential election.

referendum

Dummy variable for a referendum.

early_election

Dummy variable for an early election.

repeat_election

Dummy variable for a repeated election.

federal

Dummy variable for a federal election.

local

Dummy variable for a local election.

municipal

Dummy variable for a municipal election.

provincial

Dummy variable for a provincial election.

mission_type

Type of monitoring mission.

mission_type2

Further specification of the monitoring mission type.

needs_assesment_m

Dummy variable for a Needs assessment mission.

election_assessment_m

Dummy variable for an election assessment mission.

expert_team_m

Dummy variable for an expert team mission.

observation_m

Dummy variable for an election observation mission.

limited_observ_m

Dummy variable for a limited election observation mission.

support_team_m

Dummy variable for a support team mission.

referendum_m

Dummy variable for a referendum observation mission.

country

Full name of the country where the election is observed.

region

Binary category for countries being traditionally associated with the political West (1) or the East (2).

region2

Political regions of Europe: Western democracies (including Europe) [11]; Western democracies (excluding Europe) [12]; Post-soviet countries (excluding Baltic states) [21], Western Balkans [22]; Southeast Europe (excluding Western Balkans) [23]; Central Europe [24]; Baltic states [25]; Central Asia [26]; others [0].

link_pdf

Link to a report in PDF format.

ecb_code

Country code in the European Central Bank database.

un_code

Country code in the United Nations database.

wb_code

Country code in the World Bank database.

wvs_code

Country code in the World Values Survey database.

eurostat_code

Country code in the Eurostat database.

politIV_code

Country code in the PolityIV database.

cw_code

Country code in the Correlates of War database.

vdem_code

Country code in the V-Dem database.

nelda_code1

Country code in the NELDA database (first round; P1 suffix).

nelda_code2

Country code in the NELDA database (second round; P2 suffix)

mission_opening

Date when the mission started.

ct_departure

Date when the core team left the country.

lto_deployment

Date when the long-term observers were deployed.

lto_departure

Date when the long-term observers left the country.

sto_deployment

Date when the short-term observers were deployed (first/single round).

sto_departure

Date when the short-term observers left the country (first/single round).

sto_arrival_second_round

Date when the short-term observers were deployed (second round).

sto_departure_second_round

Date when the short-term observers left the country (second round).

ct_nationality

Link to documentation on core team members' nationality.

lto_nationality

Link to documentation on long-term observers' nationality.

corpus_id

Unique corpus id enumerating every section extracted from PDF files. Each row has its unique id.

heading

Raw section headings extracted from PDF files.

heading_clean

Cleaned and standardized section headings.

level

Heading level. The main level is 1. If a section contains subsections, they are level 2 entries.

tag

Categorical tag characterizing the section/text based on its heading: summary, background, election_day, results, misc, conclusions, recommendations, introduction, pre_election, campaign, counting, legal_framework, administration, voter_registration, media, voting, complaints, candidate_registration, tabulation, minorities, observation, post_election, electoral_system, campaign_finance, women, NVT (*new voting technologies*).

text

Raw sections of text extracted from PDF files. Each section is cleaned and standardized. Sections per report are organized in sequence, replicating their natural position in the original document. More formally, a text refers to any chapter or its distinguished subsections (having a heading) in written reports which are extracted and stored in tabular format for easy processing.

lem

Lemmatized version of the original text. Lemmatization was done using Trankit processing pipeline with the default English model. Apart from the main corpus, the repository also contains fully annotated texts in the standard CoNLL-U format.